

ISic0090

I.Sicily inscription 0090

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Divo

2. Commodo

3. Aug(usto)

4. d(ecreto) d(ecurionum)

5. p(ecunia) p(ublica)

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284838

EDR 109665

EDCS 22100043

Bibliography

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Manganaro, G. 1988. *La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. ANRW.* 2.11.1: 3-89. At 76

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